

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF PORTLAND CEMENT TERNARY PASTE WITH NANOSILICA (NS) AND METAKAOLIN (MK) AT EARLY HYDRATION AGES

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ABSTRACT

The production of high-performance cementitious compounds with supplementary cementitious materials (SCM), such as metakaolin (MK) and nanosilica (NS), can generate synergistic effects on the cementitious matrix, altering the properties and molecular structure of C-S-H, especially at early hydration ages. This article proposes to carry out an evaluation of the compressive strength and microstructural alterations of ternary mixtures using NS and MK at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days. At all early ages, it was verified that the 13MK2NS paste showed superior compressive strength to the ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) paste and that the peak of C-S-H occurred more quickly with greater heat flow. From the TG/DTG and FTIR tests, there was a greater consumption of calcium hydroxide (CH) by the ternary mixture 13MK2NS, mainly after 3 days of hydration. From Si^{29} NMR, it was also verified that the synergistic effects between NS and MK favors a greater incorporation of aluminium in the C-A-S-H structure at ages 1, 3, and 7 days. The results indicate that the synergistic effect between MK and NS occurs continuously throughout hydration from 1 day of hydration to, more expressively, 7 days.

KEYWORDS: Nanosilica, metakaolin, synergistic effects, C-A-S-H

I. INTRODUCTION

Supplementary cementitious materials (SCM) have been used by the cement industry as a strategy to reduce the clinker content of the types of cement produced [1-9]. Among the alternatives of supplementary cementitious materials (SCM) for the production of High-Performance Concrete (HPC), the use of metakaolin (MK) and nanosilica (NS) in isolation allows the formation of a more efficient composite. Metakaolin (MK) is a pozzolanic material originating from the calcination of kaolinite clays

at temperatures ranging from 500 to 800 °C, while nanosilica (NS) is a nanoscale technology that has been introduced as an advanced pozzolan [10].

The incorporation of MK causes changes in the chemical composition of hydrate with the formation of C-A-S-H. When considering that the constitution of MK is high in aluminum, the incorporation of aluminum into the C-A-S-H structure can be considered as one of the reasons that affect the properties of the cementitious structure [11-14]. When analyzing the mechanical properties of mixtures with MK, it is observed that there is a decrease in resistance at ages of 3 and 7 days, with replacement levels between 10 and 20%. This can be attributed to the pozzolanic reaction in MK not being well developed at these ages and the filler effect not being able to repair the clinker reduction. Neto et al. [20] mentions that MK can also modify the hydration kinetics of the mixture, increasing the probability of undersulfation occurring.

Among the available nanomaterials, authors such as Roychand et al. [21] cite nanosilica as a material with high potential for improving the properties of cement composites. Garcia-Taengua et al [22] mentions that NS properly dosed in the cement mixture is capable of increasing the performance of the mixture through 3 mechanisms, filler effect, nucleation effect and pozzolanic effect, and these mechanisms can be observed through modifications in the cement matrix at early ages.

An increase in the performance of the cement matrix can be achieved with the joint use of MK and NS, both in terms of mechanical resistance and material durability [23-26]. Furthermore, changes in the microstructure are evident from the analysis of the C-S-H/C-A-S-H formed, highlighting the synergy of these two materials [19, 27-34]. These studies show that there is a better synergistic effect between MK and NS, reflecting increased compressive strength and microstructural changes, such as high CH intake and increased mean chain length (MCL) of C-S-H/C-A-S-H.

Jamsheer et al. [27] addresses the aspect that the use of NS in the cement mixture favors the formation of a more refined porous structure and, additionally, the introduction of MK into the mixture increases the probability of formation of C-A-S-H. Authors such as Sousa and Rêgo [34] evaluated the nanosilica/metakaolin ratio in the formation of C-A-S-H and through the parameter f . They observed that in the ternary mixture about 1/5 of the tetrahedral sites were occupied by aluminum. Jamsheer et al. [27] and Sousa and Rêgo [34] found that after 28 days, the average size of the C-A-S-H chain was higher in ternary mixtures, compared to reference and binary mixtures.

Although some studies present analyses of mixtures containing MK and NS, none of these studies have proposed to understand the age at which synergy has already been verified between these two components deeply. Considering that no researches are focusing on the hydration of mixtures containing MK and NS in the initial ages, this article proposes to complement the research esplanade on the theme of ternary cement mixtures, developing a study that evaluates hydration in the initial ages 1, 3 and 7 days of ternary mixtures of Portland cement containing MK and NS.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Materials

The materials used in this article were: Type V Portland Cement (OPC), according to Brazilian Standard NBR 7215 (1996), HP Ultra Metacaulim (MK) produced by Metacaulim do Brasil, Colloidal Nanosilica (NS) with 30% solids content, produced by AkzoNobel; and Superplasticizing Additive (SP), Master-Glenium 51 produced by BASF.

To use the colloidal NS, drying was carried out in an oven for 48h to perform the loss of ignition (LOI) test. The chemical compositions of OPC, MK and NS are presented in Table 1, obtained by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF). From the OPC and MK laser granulometry test, an average diameter of 14.05 μm and 15.85 μm , respectively, was observed. The specific surface area of OPC, MK and NS was 1.00 m^2/g , 18.05 m^2/g , 80 m^2/g , respectively.

Table 1. Chemical and physical composition of OPC, MK and NS cement

Properties	OPC	MK	NS
SiO ₂	20.85	58.1	94.84
Al ₂ O ₃	4.64	33.28	0.15

Chemical composition (%)	MgO	5.10	0.12	<0.01
	Fe ₂ O ₃	3.08	2.21	<0.01
	CaO	58.33	0.11	<0.01
	In ₂ O	0.39	-	1.96
	K ₂ O	1.05	1.62	<0.01
	TiO ₂	0.25	1.47	<0.01
	P ₂ O ₅	0.16	0.11	<0.01
	MnO	<0.01	-	<0.01
	SO ₃	4.07	0.11	-
	Other	<0.01	-	<0.01
	Loss of ignition	2.69	2.38	3.10
Granulometry	d10 (µm)	2.63	2.06	-
	d50 (µm)	12.51	12.17	-
	d90 (µm)	45.00	71.00	-
	Average diameter (µm)	14.05	15.85	-
Specific surface (m ² /g)		1.00	18.05	80*
Density (g/cm ³)		3.05	2.56*	-

*Data provided by manufacturer

X-ray diffraction patterns were also found for OPC (Fig. 1.a), NS (Fig. 1.b) and MK (Fig. 1.c). A Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer with voltage of 40kV and amperage of 40mA was used. The sweep speed was 15 rpm, from 3 to 100° 2θ. Compounds such as larnite (C₂S), tricalcium silicate (C₃S), anhydrous calcium ferroaluminate (C₄AF), gypsum and tricalcium aluminate (C₃A) were found in the cement diffractogram. No peaks were detected in NS test, highlighting the amorphous nature of the material. Additionally, the X-ray diffraction test was carried out in MK, as shown in Figure 1c, in which the compounds quartz, kaolinite, anatase and muscovite were identified. The identified kaolinite indicates that there is still a quantity of this compound that did not undergo crystalline change after burning, to form reactive metakaolinite, represented by the amorphous halo.

Figure. 1. Difratograms obtained from cement (a) OPC where: 1- Larnite (C₂S); 2- Tricalcium silicate (C₃S); 3 – Anhydrous calcium ferroaluminate (C₄AF); 4- Gypsum; 5 - Tricalcium achloride (C₃A), 6- Quartz (SiO₂), 7-

Calcite (CaCO_3); (b) NS amorphous; (c) MK where: 1- Quartz (SiO_2); 2- Kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_5$); 3- Anatase (TiO_2); 4- Muscovite ($\text{KAl}_2(\text{Si}_3\text{Al})\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$).

2.2. Preparation and composition of pastes

To achieve this study objectives, the pastes needed to be analyzed at three different ages: 1, 3, and 7 days. The consistency of the pastes, measured by the mini-slump test [35], was fixed at 94 ± 10 mm, and the content of the superplasticizer was changed in each paste to achieve the determined consistency (table 2). The water content of colloidal NS and superplasticizer additive were subtracted from the total water content to maintain the same w/b ratio of 0.40 for all pastes.

The pastes were prepared in a planetary mortar mixer, with the following procedure: first, the water/NS/SP mixture was added to the mixer and then the previously homogenized OPC and MK mixture. Later, the materials were homogenized with the slow rotation of the mixer (140rpm) for 60 seconds and then with the rapid rotation (280rpm) for 90 seconds. The paste was used to shape cylindrical specimens, 50mm in diameter and 100mm in height. The specimens were placed in a humid chamber for 24 h, demolded and then cured by immersion in aqueous solution saturated with lime until the ages of testing. This procedure followed the Brazilian Standard NBR 7215/1996 with adaptations.

For each paste, 4 specimens were used for the compressive strength test. The quantitative and composition of the pastes produced are shown in Table 2. It is notable that, for the composition of the paste with NS, the water present in colloidal nanosilica solution (30% solids content) was considered, so that the water/cement ratio of 0.4 was maintained. With the materials used in the preparation of the pastes, the mixing procedure was performed to perform the isothermal calorimetry test, and after the rupture of the specimens, samples were collected for x-ray diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TG), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR ^{29}Si). The hydration of the samples was interrupted by immersion in isopropanol for 24 h, followed by drying at 40°C for 6h. After hydration paralyzed, the samples were involved in plastic film and stored in closed containers with silica gel and soda lime, to limit the interactions with moisture and CO_2 until the age of the tests. Table 2 shows that to maintain the same spreading, the paste that required the most superplasticizer additive was 13MK2NS, followed by the binary paste of MK (15MK) and the reference (OPC). The behavior presented is coherent, considering the high specific surface of the NS and low particle size of the SCM. The high SP content of the ternary paste can be justified by the combined effect of these materials.

Table 2. Composition of the pastes produced in the study

Pastes	Abbreviation	OPC (g)	MK (g)	NS content (%)	NS (g)	Colloidal NS solution (g)	SP (%)	Mini-slump diameter (mm)	Water (g)
100% OPC	OPC	2400	-	-	-	-	0.21	93.2	957.0
85% OPC + 15% MK	15MK	2040	360	-	-	-	1.05	102.7	950.59
85% OPC+13% MK +2% NS	13MK2NS	2040	312	2	48	160	1.62	94.6	825.05

2.3. Test carried out

All tests were performed at 1, 3, and 7 days of hydration. The tests of compressive strength of the specimens were performed in a universal test machine, according to Brazilian Standard NBR 7215/1996.

Isothermal calorimetry was performed with an eight-channel TAM air (TA Instruments) Thermometric calorimeter, with a computerized data acquisition system, average reading frequency every 30 seconds, and controlled temperature of 23°C for 72 h.

TGA was performed in samples of ground pastes using a Thermal Analyzer TA Instruments SDT Q60 q0. The initial mass of the samples of 10 ± 1 mg was placed in a platinum crucible, the test was performed between 50 and 800°C with a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, with an N_2 flow of $100\text{mL}/\text{min}$. From the

TG/DTG curves, the CH content was calculated from equation 1, and the CH index, which is the parameter that relates the CH content of the reference paste with the other pastes at the specified ages.

$$\text{CH content} = 4,11 * \text{volatilized water content} \tag{Equation 1 [36]}$$

The FTIR was performed in the range of 4000-400cm⁻¹ with samples of ground pastes. They were mixed with KBr (ratio 1:100). Data were recorded with a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrometer.

The ²⁹Si NMR was performed with an Ascend 600 Avance III HD Model Bruker Console, equipped with a 4 mm CP/MAS H/X probe and an applied DT magnetic field of 14.1 T (600 MHz). The test was performed at the turning frequency of 10KHz, with a pulse duration of 4.25µs and pulse interval of 10s, using a minimum of 1024 points to have each spectrum. Tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as an internal reference. The spectra obtained were deconvoluted in their elementary components with the Software TopSpin 4.1.3 Bruker, using Gaussian/Lorentzian profiles. After the deconvolution of the spectra, using the relative areas of each Qn component, it is possible to calculate two parameters that characterize the C-S-H, mean chain length (MCL) and parameter f, use for measure the fraction of spaces in the chain filled by aluminum tetrahedrons. These parameters are calculated using equations 2 and 3 [37]:

$$MCL = \frac{2}{\left(\frac{Q1}{Q1 + Q2(0Al) + \frac{3}{2}Q2(1Al) + Q3(0Al) + Q3(1Al)} \right)} \tag{Equation 2}$$

$$f = \frac{\frac{1}{2}Q2(1Al)}{\frac{3}{2}Q1 + Q2(0Al) + \frac{3}{2}Q2(1Al) + Q3(0Al) + Q3(1Al)} \tag{Equation 3}$$

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

3.1. Compressive strength

Table 3 presents the results of the compressive strength of the pastes produced in the study, as well as the Performance Index (PI) of the pastes produced, which is paste compressive strength compared to the strength of the OPC paste at the specified age. Table 3 also presents the homogeneous groups obtained with the Duncan Test. The ANOVA test was also performed, considering the pastes compositions as the independent variable and the compressive strength as the dependent variable, the results are shown in Table 4. It was verified that the pastes composition was significant in compressive strength at 1, 3 and 7 days, since the p-value found was lower than the confidence level 0,05.

Table 3 - Results of compressive strength of the pastes produced and Duncan test homogeneous at 1, 3 and 7 days

Age	Paste	Mean compressive strength (MPa)	Performance index (PI) (%)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
1 day	OPC	21,2	100	X		
	15MK	17,1	80,5	X		
	13MK2NS	32,8	154,6		X	
3 days	OPC	40,0	100	X		
	15MK	31,2	78,0	X		
	13MK2NS	44,1	110,1		X	
7 days	OPC	43,2	100	X		

	15MK	44,8	103,7	X	X	
	13MK2NS	55,0	127,4			X

Table 4 – ANOVA test parameters at 1, 3 and 7 days of hydration

Age	Dependent variable	Independent variable	<i>p</i> -value	Significance
1 day	Paste composition	Paste composition	0,000005	Yes
3 days	Paste composition	Paste composition	0,000925	Yes
7 days	Paste composition	Paste composition	0,017839	Yes

With 1 day of hydration, the 13MK2NS paste presented the highest compressive strength value with 32.8 MPa and PI of 154.6% (Group 2). This behavior of the paste that used NS can be justified by the three effects that this nanomaterial promotes: filler effect, nucleation effect, and pozzolanic effect, as cited by Wang et al. [38] and García-Taengua et al. [32], evidencing the importance of NS in this parameter. At this same age of evaluation, the 15MK paste presented lower IP with 80.5% (Group 1). This may be related to the pozzolanic reaction and, consequently, additional C-A-S-H production, which has not yet developed at this age, and by the lower clinker content in the paste.

At 3 days of hydration, the 15MK paste continued to present a lower PI of the OPC paste, with a performance index of 78.0% (Group1), according to the results obtained by Rêgo et al. [28] and Shafiq et al. [29]. The highest PI was evidenced in the 13MK2NS paste with 110.1% (Group 2).

The decrease in the performance index at 3 days of sample 13MK2NS compared to 1 day may be associated with a decrease in NS activity, given the high probability that a significant amount of NS has already reacted, so that the pozzolanic reaction attributed to MK has not yet started, as has the C-S-H layer on the clinker surface, which blocks hydration. [39-42].

The low-strength behavior of the 15MK paste at 3 days begins to change at 7 days, where the results of compressive strength are matched with the OPC paste, considering that at this age the pozzolanic reaction of the MK begins to intensify [43]. From 7 days, the 15MK paste exceeds the strength result of the OPC paste, presenting an ID of 103.72% (Group 2). At 7 days, the 13MK2NS paste presented an increase in ID 127.4% (Group 3), indicating the intensification of the pozzolanic reaction of MK in this period.

3.2. Isothermal calorimetry

The calorimetric curves evidencing the heat flow up to 72 h of the three pastes produced in this study are shown in Figure 2. It is possible to observe changes in the profile of the 15MK and 13MK2NS curves along all stages of hydration when compared to the OPC, as seen in the parameters in Table 5.

Figure. 2 (a) Normalized heat flow of pastes up to 72 h of hydration and (b) Accumulated heat of the pastes produced with 72h of hydration.

Table 5 - Isothermal calorimetry analysis parameters

Sample	OPC	15MK	13MK 2NS
Test time (h)	72	72	72
Time of end of dissolution (h)	0.2759	0.2128	0.2118
Induction end time (h)	7.09	3.15	3.38
C-S-H peak heat flow (mW/g)	1.962	1.795	2.181
C-S-H peak time (h)	16.7	12.62	11.96

When analyzing the heat flow of the C-S-H peak, it was verified that the paste 13MK2NS presented the highest value, being the values of 2.181 mW/g, results that corroborate those pointed out by Antoni et al. [39], Scrivener et al. [44], Andrade et al. [19] and Zunino and Scrivener [45]. It is also noteworthy that all pastes with SCM had a formation of the peak of C-S-H occurring significantly earlier compared to the OPC mixture (16.70h).

When analyzing the 13MK2NS paste in Figure 2, it is possible to notice the formation of the admixture peak closer to the Peak of C-S-H, which shows that in this paste the phenomenon of undersulfation occurred [20-46]. This undersulfation behavior of the 13MK2NS paste can be explained by the study by Zunino and Scrivener [45], in which the authors verified that the use of SCM increases the specific surface of the matrix, and this helps the occurrence of subsulfation, taking into account that the nucleation effect increases the precipitation of C-S-H, which causes sulfate ions to be absorbed on the C-S-H surface

When analyzing the total accumulated heat of the pastes with 24h, the 13MK2NS paste presented the highest accumulated heat value in the initial hydration period up to 24h, evidencing the contribution of NS to the increase of accumulated heat, justified by the characteristics of the high reactivity of this material. With 3 days of hydration, the highest total accumulated heat of the pastes followed the decreasing order: OPC, 13MK2NS, and 15MK, as seen in Figure 2. The lowest accumulated total heat values were identified in the pastes containing MK, which is explained by the decrease in hydration of C3S, due to the substitution of 15% of clinker in pastes with MK and by the pozzolanic reaction of MK has not yet occurred in greater intensity at 3 days of hydration.

3.3. Thermogravimetry (TG/DTG)

The TG/DTG curves of the pastes tested at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days are shown in Figure 3, respectively. The evaluation and comparison of the calculated CH contents and the CH index to the OPC pastes are shown in Table 6.

Figure. 3 TG and DTG curves of pastes with (a) 1 day hydration, (b) 3 days and (c) 7 days

Table 6 - Parameters obtained from mass loss and DTG curves at ages 1, 3 and 7 days

PASTES	1 day			3 days			7 days		
	CH (%)	T.CH (%)	I.CH	CH (%)	T.CH (%)	I.CH	CH (%)	T.CH (%)	I.CH
OPC	3.61	14.83	100	4.22	17.36	100	4.29	17.64	100
15MK	3.57	14.68	98.96	3.16	12.98	74.80	2.94	12.08	68.50
13MK2NS	3.26	13.39	90.29	2.69	11.07	63.79	2.53	10.40	58.93

With 1 day of hydration, the lowest I.CH was evidenced in the 13MK2NS paste, with 90,29%. Singh et al. [46] attributes this behavior of high CH consumption of pastes with NS, mainly to the nucleation effect provided by this nanomaterial and also to the high specific surface area, as pointed out by Zhao et al. [47]. The 15MK paste, presented I.CH 98,96, attributed to the acceleration of clinker hydration by increasing nucleation points, favoring hydration without running the pozzolanic reaction of MK.

At 3 days of hydration, the behavior of pastes with SCM presented lower I.CH compared with the OPC paste is observed. The lowest I.CH were evidenced in the pastes 13MK2NS and 15MK, 63,79% and 74,80%, respectively. At this age, it is already possible to observe the onset of pozzolanic reactions of MK that led to an increase in CH consumption in the 15MK paste at 3 days concerning 15MK paste with 1 day.

At 7 days, it is possible to verify that the ternary paste 13MK2NS presents a high consumption of CH with the lowest I.CH, 58,93% among all pastes produced at all ages, which reinforces the synergy between the components already mentioned above. The behavior of the ternary paste indicates that while the chemical reaction of NS tended to stabilize at 3 days, the effects of MK on the paste occurred, thus promoting the formation of an intersection point. These results are in agreement with the studies of Sousa [34], which presented I.CH of these ternary pastes MK/NS at 7 days of 61.61% and 55.17%, for pastes with different MK/NS ratios. After 1, 3 and 7 days, the levels of hydrated phases were evaluated based on the mass loss in the range of 50 to 450°C, which is related to the dehydroxylation of the main phases formed during the Portland cement hydration process [48-50]. The hydrated phase content was used to calculate a Hydrated Phase Index (HP index) for the pastes, which directly compares them with the OPC paste. Table 7 compiles the results.

3.4. Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Figure 4 shows the FTIR spectra of the OPC, 15MK, and 13MK2NS samples with 1, 3, and 7 days of hydration. For the evaluation of the hydrates formed, two regions were analyzed, the one referring to CH at peak 3643 cm^{-1} and C-A-S-H at peak 971 cm^{-1} . Taking into consideration the semiquantitative character of the technique, the transmittance values indicate the contents of each compound of the pastes, so the lower the transmittance value, the greater the amount of the compound in the matrix.

Figure. 4 Infrared spectra in the CH and C-S-H regions with (a) 1 day hydration, (b) 3 days hydration and (c) 7 days hydration

The semi-quantitative method of FTIR applied in this study was that proposed by Andrade et al. [19]. These authors verified that at 28 days, there was a decrease in the intensity of the peak of CH, which reflects on CH consumption, of ternary pastes when compared to the other pastes produced with other SCM. This behavior described at 28 days was verified in this study at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days, as seen in the spectra of Figure 4.

When evaluating the spectrum region referring to CH at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days, it is verified that the transmittance values are lower for the OPC paste, justified by the absence of a compound that reacts with CH in the cement matrix, which reflects the absence of CH consumption, followed by the 15MK and 13MK2NS pastes.

When analyzing the spectrum region referring to C-S-H at ages 1, 3, and 7 days, it was verified that the lowest transmittance values were detected in the 13MK2NS paste, suggesting the greater formation of C-S-H/C-A-S-H, a result that is in line with those of compressive strength presented in table 3.

Studies that have been published on the theme of ternary pastes with MK and NS evaluate cementitious matrices only at the age of 28 days. Jamsheer et al. [27] observed that the use of NS and MK promoted an elongation in the Si-O bond, which is directly related to the incorporation of aluminum in the C-S-H chain. This elongation in the Si-O bond indicating that the inclusion of aluminum in the C-S-H chain has been happening since the first day of hydration, when compared to the other pastes, can be seen in 13MK2NS pastes at 1, 3, and 7 days.

3.4. Nuclear magnetic resonance imaging (^{29}Si NMR)

The ^{29}Si NMR results containing their respective deconvoluted spectra and the curves resulting from the deconvolutions of the peaks used for analysis are shown in Figures 5, at the ages of 1 day, 3 days, and 7 days hydration. Table 7 gathers the results of ^{29}Si NMR for pastes produced at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days.

Figure. 5 Results of ²⁹Si NMR for the pastes produced with 1 day, 3 days and 7 days

Table 7- MCL and parameter f for OPC, 15MK and 13MK2NS pastes at ages 1, 3 and 7 days.

Age	Pastes	MCL	Parameter f
		Richardson [37]	
1 day	OPC	5.57	0.131
	15MK	4.76	0.132
	13MK2NS	6.36	0.140
3 days	OPC	5.36	0.144
	15MK	4.98	0.117
	13MK2NS	6.65	0.149
7 days	OPC	5.45	0.140
	15MK	10.33	0.162
	13MK2NS	10.78	0.207

When evaluating the initial hydration period at the age of 1 day, the highest values of MCL with 6.36 in the 13MK2NS paste were verified. This behavior can be justified by the high reactivity of NS and rapid initial reaction that favors the entry of silicon into the C-S-H structure, already evidenced by the studies by Pérez et al. [49] and by the results of mechanical strength (Table 3). The MCL results of the 13MK2NS paste indicate that in this period there is already a synergistic interaction between NS and MK, considering that even with lower clinker content (85%) the paste 13MK2NS can stand out in the MCL value when compared to the other pastes.

It is noteworthy that with 1 day of hydration, the 15MK paste did not reach an MCL value similar to the OPC paste, which evidences a slower reactive behavior of this paste at this age, also taking into account the low consumption of CH obtained from the TG/DTG tests (Table 6), and the low compressive strength at this same age (Table 3).

At 3 days of hydration, the 15MK paste showed an increase in the MCL value to the age of 1 day, however, there was still a lower value than the OPC paste. The 13MK2NS paste presented the highest MCL value, reflecting the increase in the relative area of Q2, to the other pastes with 3 days of hydration and, mainly, in the Q2(1Al) fraction, resulting from the insertion of aluminium from the C-S-H chain.

Additionally, it is possible to verify a trend of progressive increase of MCL in 15MK and 13MK2NS pastes, since the pozzolanic reaction of MK starts at 3 days and intensifies from days of hydration. At

7 days of hydration, the pastes 13MK2NS and 15MK presented the highest values of MCL, with 10.78 and 10.33, respectively. When analyzing the results presented in Table 7, it is proven that the combination of MK and NS promotes changes in the chemical structure of C-A-S-H since 1 day of hydration, presenting the highest values of MCL with 1, 3, and 7 days, when compared with the other pastes.

Table 7 presents the f parameter values, corresponding to the amount of aluminum inserted from the structure of C-S-H/C-A-S-H, of the pastes at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days. Considering that parameter f measures the fraction of spaces in the chain filled by aluminum tetrahedrons, it is observed that the ternary paste 13MK2NS generated a higher f value, with 0.140, 0.149, and 0.207 to 1, 3, and 7 days, respectively, which demonstrates the effect of NS, in facilitating the inclusion of aluminum in the C-A-S-H chain. Moreover, with the results of parameter f , it can be assumed that around 20% of the tetrahedron spaces are needed for aluminum tetrahedron in the C-A-S-H composition, as seen by Sousa and Rêgo [34] at 28 days.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

By analyzing the results in this article, it is possible to reach the following conclusions.

At the initial ages of 1, 3, and 7 days, the use of NS was a fundamental factor for compressive strength gain. The ternary mixture 13MK2NS showed higher compressive strength among the pastes, which evidences the synergy between these materials, whereas even with the replacement of 15% of clinker it was possible to obtain mechanical results superior to the OPC paste.

The paste 13MK2NS showed heat release and a more accelerated reaction, compared to the other, evidenced by the formation of the peak of C-S-H/C-A-S-H more rapidly. Considering that the 13MK2NS paste had undersulfation, it is possible to infer that the results of mechanical strength of the sample at the ages of 1, 3, and 7 days could have been greater if there had been a balance of sulfate in the cementitious matrix;

The quantitative (TG/DTG) and semi-quantitative (FTIR) results of calcium hydroxide (CH) intake showed that the ternary paste (13MK2NS) showed the most expressive behavior in the consumption of CH from the pozzolanic reaction, among the pastes produced, mainly from the 3 days of hydration.

Although the isolated use of MK did not contribute to the increase of the MCL of the C-S-H/C-A-S-H chain with 1 and 3 days of hydration, the combined use with NS favored the progressive increase of MCL, indicating the importance of NS for aluminum incorporation for the formation of C-A-S-H since 1 day hydration.

The chemical changes resulting from the synergy of these SCM, such as high consumption of calcium hydroxide (CH), incorporation of aluminum in the C-S-H/C-A-S-H chain and increase in MCL, directly influenced the mechanical properties of the paste produced, which resulted in compounds with more efficient performance when compared to the others. Thus, the results indicate that the synergistic effect of MK and NS occurs continuously throughout the hydration period, starting from 1 day, due to the contribution of NS, and intensifying from 3 days onwards, due to the contribution of MK.

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